

Review Article

The Nigerian Factor Vis a Vis the COVID-19 Safety Protocols: Digital
Theatre As a Panacea

Ihuoma Okorie

Department of Theatre and Performing Arts, Bayero University, Kano
Okorieihuoma4@gmail.com

Abstract

The “Nigerian factor”, seen as an acquired value system and mindset which impedes the realization of certain pertinent goals in the society, is one which often manifests in the attitude and behaviour of Nigerians, to the extent that it has become the biggest challenge in the fight against the Corona virus pandemic. Using the medium theory, this paper analyses two drama skits created by the Nigerian popular Theatre Alliance, on the need to observe safety guidelines and also address some misconceptions surrounding the eradication of the virus. This was achieved through the intercourse between the theatre and social media. Findings reveal that through the digital theatre, resulting from the intercourse between the Theatre and social media, the power of theatre was popularised, as the actors turned out to be indirect activists addressing the audience on the need to observe safety protocols. Theatre here, served as a vehicle for information dissemination, on the need to observe the laid down guidelines. Therefore, considering the fact that the pandemic still subsists, this paper suggests that theatre should be deployed to reach out to a wider audience on the safety protocols to be observed. It further recommends that theatre practitioners devise better ways of embracing the new media platforms and outlets to reach out to the larger audience on other pressing issues in the society.

Keywords: Digital Theatre, Nigerian factor, Social Media, Nigerian Popular Theatre Alliance.

Received: 12/08/20

Accepted: 30/11/20

Introduction

Corona virus, (COVID-19) is an infectious disease which causes respiratory infections ranging from common colds to severe cold, causing respiratory difficulties. Accordingly, Shereen et al (2020: 93) notes that the virus was believed to have originated from the Hunan seafood market at Wuhan, China

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where live bats, snakes and wild animals were sold in December, 2019. However, it was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organisation on 11th March, 2020. In Nigeria, the virus arrived in the body of an Italian man, who came into the country in February, 2020. As a result, Nigeria in trying to curb the rapid spread authorized the lockdown of the country while some state governors took proactive steps by locking down borders, markets and social gatherings. For a while, people took the safety measures seriously; however, as time went by, they got tired and began to display a lack luster attitude. However, Nigerians have continued to pay less attention to the safety measures, reeled out by the National Centre for Disease and Control, (NCDC) which are meant to be strictly adhered to, in order to avoid a spike. Despite all, targeted messages on the need to adhere to the safety guidelines have continued to trend and fill the airwaves but the level of adherence is still low, especially in some places. This clearly shows that there is the need to deploy an alternative medium for this purpose considering the negative trait that Nigerians have imbibed, known as the “Nigerian Factor”. However, one medium that has not been adequately explored is the digital theatre which is the marriage between the Theatre and social media. Therefore, the aim this paper is to analyse the drama skits performed by the National Popular Theatre Alliance, focusing on how well the messages concerning the safety guidelines were communicated and disseminated via the use of the social media.

The Problem

There is no gainsaying that COVID-19 has affected livelihoods of thousands of Nigerians, especially those who are battling calamities such as health crisis, acute food shortage, which has in turn, left communities vulnerable to the disease. On the other hand, several ironies are springing up especially from this part of the world where many still do not believe that the Corona virus is real; to this end, some are very carefree and non-challant about it. This has resulted in a declining rate in the covid-19 compliance; in fact, it has continued to exacerbate, considering the fact that the number of infected people as well as the mortality rate is on the decline. As a result, individuals are getting complacent at every level. Part of the problem lies in the fact that Nigeria is a huge country with many different languages and high illiteracy rates among people living in rural areas. As a result, problems associated with not having adequate knowledge about the safety protocols as well as the spread of the deadly pandemic is imminent, especially for those who do not understand the English language. Moreover, messages reeled out through various mediums often carry out their media campaigns using the English language, which is not understood by all. Thus, this study takes a critical look

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at the medium deployed, the content and how effectively, the message was disseminated.

Literature

The spread of the novel corona-virus is recorded daily in the number of infections reported in Nigeria despite the safety measures and guidelines that has been put in place by the World Health Organisation, (WHO) reiterated by the National Centre for Disease and Control, (NCDC). For this reason, Ihuoma (2020) asserts that the basic factor militating against these preventive and control measures is known as the “Nigerian factor”. Though, perceived by some as an embodiment of failure, Ihuoma (2020) explains that

The Nigerian factor is a set of activities or practices which are not innate but are an acquired value system and mindset which impedes the realization of certain pertinent goals. It is an act of disobedience, “breaking rules” and “disruptive behaviour” by some people who see everything wrong with the directives put in place by those in authority which affects the collective interest and growth of the nation and of particular emphasis, the containment and subsequent eradication of the COVID 19 pandemic.

As stated the Nigerian factor is now very much politically, socially and morally acceptable to the extent that it has become a norm among the populace, it has become an ailment which is seen as a normal socio-cultural way of life peculiar to Nigerians. Therefore, propagating and spreading the message concerning the safety guidelines is paramount and cannot be over emphasised. Though, media outlets like the print and the electronic media have been used to disseminate information on the need to adhere to the safety guidelines, however, the role of art with emphasis on theatre shall be looked into. This underscores the fact that in a time of health crisis, the role of art becomes central. Its importance is further expressed by Netter (2020) who states that:

We ought to move to a place we have perhaps, neglected. Of all the necessities, we know feel so keenly aware of, the arts and their contribution to our wellbeing. The arts around the world are adapting to shutdowns by swapping physical performance spaces for virtual ones because with audiences isolating at home, venues shuttered, the arts have responded to this challenge with the kind of ingenuity you expect from highly creative minds.

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From the above, it can be alludes that finding creative ways to disseminate information concerning the virus that have kept people apart cannot be over emphasised hence, the role of the arts. As regards, Boal (1974) points out that the purpose of art should not be to provide aesthetic pleasure or an escape from reality but to contribute to society's ongoing attempts to solve its problems through opening new avenues for thoughts, discussion and action. Accordingly, Boal's idea concerning art is pertinent because the art's on its own is a medium of communication that can be used to disseminate information in the society considering its ability to reach many people. Thus depending on the medium deployed in a certain situation, art has a crucial role to play in the society. Particularly, there has been growing interest in recent times concerning the contribution of theatre to address significant social messages, like the communication of health related message. In fact, a range of retrospective and prospective studies have gathered evidence capturing the perceived benefits of Theatre. One among the numerous that exists is that of Zazzali (2013) who explains that :

Theatre can be seen as a variety of art forms showcased in and outside the building; for instance, activities that man engages in which shows the relationship between humans and the society. This is often achieved by man, trying to penetrate the deep mystery of life and consciously develops theatre in order to correct what is wrong; this is what makes man a gregarious animal.

From the above, it can be deciphered that theatre is more than just a performance; it is a place for human encounter as well as a space for authentic human existence. Therefore, theatre is one art form that possesses the ability to disseminate information on a variety of issues in the society.

Particularly, there is a growing body of literature on the role of theatre in disseminating information's concerning health crisis in the society. Firstly, Mbizvo (2006) notes that theatre has proven to be an effective and entertaining strategy for dissemination of information's regarding health messages, in both the rural and urban settings of Africa. For this reason, Mbizvo (2006) explains that :

The content of any theatre production with a goal of health promotion should be derived from a realistic assessment of the knowledge, attitudes and behavior of the prospective audience. In this regard, Theatre can overcome literacy barriers through use of local experience and vernacular to provoke emotional and analytical responses in the audience.

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From the above, it is clear that the role of theatre in disseminating information regarding health issues cannot be over emphasised. Moreover, performance always adapts because it is an integral part of the human experience, seen as the way we relate to each other and make sense of the world. This is why Boal (1974) sees theatre as a weapon and mirror to the world, one that we can reach into, to change our reality.

Specifically, Massar, Sialubanje and Maltagliati (2018) while exploring the perceived effectiveness of Theatre as a Maternal Health Promotion tool states that a sizeable number of people are positive about the use of Theatre interventions in improving maternal health care seeking behaviour. He notes that its effectiveness was showcased in the incorporation of theatre plays which resulted to unique contributions and possibilities of utilizing theatre in health promotion.

From the above, it is clear that the effectiveness of theatre in promoting health related messages cannot be overemphasized considering the successes it has recorded in terms of achieving behaviour change in different endeavours. Though, one of the oldest forms of communication, which has been used to achieve Behaviour change, education and therapy, exploring its intercourse with the social media especially in times of pandemics has not be fully explored hence, the utmost need for this study.

Thus, building on the above, this paper discusses the benefits of the digital theatre which is a coalition between theatre and social media, in a pandemic period. As seen, the very nature of our current situation means that almost all live performances ceased globally. However, with the theatre buildings closed, theatre still found a way of getting to the populace. In fact, there have been a number of live staged readings of plays and musicals through platforms like zoom; some have gone ahead to make performances for live streaming. As discussed, theatre here is patently, not tied to theatres as the presence of a public building; this is because it is no longer a necessity for performance. Many theatre practitioners began creating innovative online work during the pandemic. This study shall take a critical look at two drama skits, performed by the National Popular Theatre Alliance (NPTA) on the need to obey safety guidelines that has been put in place and to de-emphasise some misconceptions that people have come to believe.

Medium Theory

Accordingly, (Mayrowitz: 2009:16) explains that the term “medium theory” was coined in the 1980s to point to the theoretical commonalities underlining the work of a number of 20th century scholars. The theory says that medium is

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the message; with specific regard to how they awaken and alter thoughts and senses. The roots of medium theory perspective lie in antiquity as humans made conscious choices regarding which media might be best to convey (and preserve) certain messages. This is because different media foster different communication patterns hence, the use of theatre as a viable medium to convey messages, regarding the safety protocols that should be adhered to in order to prevent a spike of the virus.. Thus, this paper analyses the capability of theatre as a mass medium, to convey messages that can help to awaken people on the need to observe safety protocols. It is also believed that there is a symbiotic relationship between the medium and the message; hence, how the message is perceived depends on the influence of the medium deployed. Though, different mediums have been deployed to convey messages regarding on the safety guidelines of COVID-19, theatre in the context of this paper is seen as a communication medium which performs various functions such as information, instructive, persuasive, education, entertainment and the development function

Analyses of both Plays by the Nigerian Popular Theatre Alliance

The Nigerian Popular Theatre Alliance, (NPTA) is a non-profit non-governmental organisation founded in 1989 with the mandate to promote participatory engagement of ordinary Nigerians in the development process. In the years that it has been in existence, NPTA has executed several projects in different parts of Nigeria. In all the projects, the Organisation was concerned with capacity building, skills development, as well as promoting people's ability to take action, to improve their own lives and to engage community development. Sequel to the afore-stated, TFDC was established in 2000 as a research and training unit of the Nigerian Popular Theatre Alliance (NPTA), a network of people and organizations in Nigeria using performing arts as a means to participatory development. TFDC is affiliated to the Development of Theatre and Performing Arts in Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Zaria, which played a pioneering role in establishing Theatre for Development as an academic field of study and action in Nigeria. The mission statement pursues social development by sharing with people inside and outside the academic context the wealth of experience with participatory development strategies built since 1989 when NPTA was founded. Among these strategies is the use of Theatre

In the first skit titled "House mates", shot for 3minutes and 17 seconds, we see a young man seated in his house while his friend enters with some bottles and leaves which are supposed to be herbs. As soon as his friend comes close, he puts on his face mask and also drops sanitizer in his hands, even though he was hesitant to use it and kept on asking what it is. In the conversation that

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ensued, his house mate informs him that he went to the market to buy some herbs that will help him fight the corona virus. His house mate starring at the items surprised asked him what they are actually meant for. In explaining to him, he tells him that he intends to mix garlic and chloroquine tablets saying that when he finishes taking the mixed herbs and alcohol, he would go ahead and steam himself, this action according to him would make him totally free from contacting the virus.

Replying, his friend, he reminds him of the fact that ignorance is actually a disease, stating that if he attempts to take all the items he bought, he will definitely end up in the grave. Rather than taking all the mixtures he bought, his friend tells him to always wash his hands with soap and running water or use an alcohol based sanitizer whenever he goes out and returns. After performing the above ritual, he should make it a point of duty to always have his bath and wash his clothes whenever he goes out and returns,

The friend later asks a question concerning the alcohol based content in the sanitizer, as to the fact that people were told to use it because of the alcohol content, his friend replies by telling him that the alcohol content is about 60%. Laughing, he begins to bring out drinks he bought telling him the percentage of the alcohol in each of them, saying that if he mixes all of them in a drink, it would have exceeded the 60% of alcohol in the sanitizer, his friend tells him of the tragedy that will befall him if he tries that as the alcohol being referred to is different and usage, wrong. He further educates him on the fact that if he is not careful, he will come down with the virus. Thus, as a way to further educate him, on the safety protocols, he offers him a face mask and a sanitizer.

The second skit titled "Amarya's house" begins with a woman who was trying the clean up her house when her husband comes in from a trip to Lagos and hands her, a gift which she declines on account of the fact that her husband did not wear a face mask neither did he wash his hands on returning home. The angry husband asked what the problem is and she replies by asking whether he is not aware of the news about the virus. He responded by saying that the virus is yet to get to where they are. However, his wife's insistence on him taking precautionary measures gets him angry to the extent that he tells her that she would be divorced if she continues. She begins to lecture him on the number of cases that have been discovered, stating that the virus does not only infect the rich but also the poor. Thus, he should try as much as possible to maintain social distancing and always ensure that he washes his hand with soap and running water when necessary because the virus is real.

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Analysis/Findings

The quote, “If you prescribe me medicine, you will cure me for a day. But if you teach me to prevent disease, you will cure me for life” sums up the ideas propagated in the drama skits, analysed above. Both stories reel out messages on the precautionary measures to be adopted by all and sundry, regarding the covid-19 safety protocols like social distancing, washing of hands with soap and running water, wearing of face masks amongst others. The essence of the skit was to raise awareness about the pandemic and the guidelines to be followed.

By deploying entertainment education as a tool, it is clear that both skits, communicates the utmost need for people to take precautionary measures in guarding themselves against the pandemic. Even more, the misconception that the virus only affects the rich and not the poor as some people actually think was de-emphasised in the skit; this is in a bid to ensure that people debunk such statement. Furthermore, contrary to what some people think, regarding the assertion that they could actually be free from the virus when they ingest alcohol, these skits tried to deflate the idea by stating clearly, the difference between alcohol and alcohol based content.

From the above, it can be clearly seen that Theatre can be a panacea in tackling the negative trait known as “The Nigerian Factor” The performers created something similar to “public service announcements” which helped to spread the word about the proper safety protocols to be imbibed in order to combat the virus. They went public with their awareness through the medium of theatre and brought critical awareness at a crucial time. Social media was used to document and reel out pertinent information which inspired, informed, gave people hope and further empowered them to observe safety protocols. Thus, digital theatre, which combines the theatre and social media platforms have been proved to be an effective vehicle for communicating information about safety protocols. The goal of the skits is not only to provide a solution but to provide a variety of ways via which safety protocols concerning the pandemic can be followed. The performers played a key role by educating and encouraging the people to obey the guidelines, as promulgated by the World Health Organisation.. They further helped to cut through the noise of the misconceptions and rumors associated with the guidelines of the pandemic. Thus, we see that theatre can appropriately address health issues by focusing on prevention and care.

From this, we can see the power of theatre to disseminate information regarding the safety protocols that should be observed as the pandemic encroaches on and emasculates the world. It was utilized as an active tool for

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proper dissemination of plausible information. Relating this to the medium theory, it is clear that digital theatre performed an informative function by reminding the audience of the need to adhere to the safety protocols. Its instructive and persuasive function was further showcased in the way the performers took their time to instruct and persuade the audience on why they ought to observe the safety guidelines. This was achieved through education and entertainment as some of the scenes were filled with humors which were indirectly used to pass across pertinent messages. This further proved that entertainment can be an effective form of information, Education, persuasion, instruction and development considering the fact that it has the power to provoke analytical responses as the content is based upon a realistic assessment of the levels of knowledge held by the target audience. This to a large extent would help in the development of the individual who would in turn, develop his society; this form of development can only be achieved when one is hale and hearty.

The platforms through which the recorded skits went digital include Whatsapp, Instagram and Face book. In exploring these new performative spaces, artists are forging new relationships with a variety of audiences. These new performance spaces force a different kind of intimacy that offers audiences a new kind of experience. Even though they are were not physically in the same space together, there is a connection forged in that exchange. From the above, we see that theatre is charting unknown territory and redefining how we think of the very concept of performing live and communicating important messages. In all, COVID-19 is apparently a war that will be won through observing proper hygiene and safety protocols. Therefore, this paper has clearly showcased how digital theatre functions as a tool to disseminate information by creating awareness on vital issues regarding COVID-19.

Conclusion

The increasing interest in the use of theatre to improve the health and wellbeing of people in the society cannot be overemphasized. This paper is one which clearly buttressed how; streamed versions of pre-recorded theatrical productions have been utilized to make impact in the society by communicating a pertinent health issue (Covid-19) in the society. This clearly shows that the theatre is a potent medium that can be used to disseminate messages concerning the safety protocols and also corrects the misconceptions surrounding the Corona virus. It was effectively used in breaking down barriers and promoting health education especially among the non-literate in communities who only understand their language and dialect. The

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combination of Hausa, English and Pidgin was used to sensitise people who do not understand the English language on the issue of COVID-19. Through the skits, the practical realities that confront and surround a people was dealt with critically which hints the people on the fact that theatre helps to break down barriers. This further exposed the fact that as a people, there is the utmost need to do things differently. Thus, the current explosion of digital theatre is one that can be deployed in different situations to make mind blowing impacts. Therefore, renegotiated and re-imagined ideas of access, community and interactivity, borne out of necessity, are an opportunity to rethink theatre. These should not be ignored rather; they should inform theatre's future.

Recommendation

- More skits surrounding stigmatization especially, as it has to do with people who have either died or recovered from the virus should be disseminated through digital theatre.
- Digital theatre should be further deployed in tackling other social issues in the society.
- Theatre practitioners can engage the public on their feed back as it relates to adhering to the safety guidelines through short performances. This can also be disseminated through the video format on social media (digital theatre).

References

Boal, A. (1974) *Theatre of the Oppressed*. New York, NY: Theatre Communications Group Inc.

Ihuoma Joy O. "Towards a COVID free Nation: The "Nigerian Factor" as a Bane"

<https://switchmedia.ng/opinion/towards-a-covid-free-nation-the-nigerian-factor-a-s-a-bane>. assessed on 21/10/2020.

Massar, K, Sialubanje, S and Maltagliati, I. (2018) *Exploring the Perceived Effectiveness of Applied Theatre as a Maternal Health Promotion Tool in Rural Zambia*. California. Sage Publications

Mbizvo, E. (2006) "Theatre -a force for health promotion". Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(06\)69917-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(06)69917-0) Dec, 1 2006

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

Meyrowitz, J. (2009) "Medium Theory : An Alternative to the dominant paradigm of Media Effects in R.L. Nabi & M.B Oliver" (Eds). *The Sage handbbok of media processes and effects*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.

Netter, L. (2020) "The importance of art in the time of Corona Virus". University of Portsmouth assessed from <https://www.the-importance-of-art-in-a-time-of-coronavirus>. Assessed on 28th October, 2020.

Shereen et al. (2020) "COVID-19 Infection: Origin, Transmission, and Characteristics of Human Coronaviruses". *Journal of Advanced Research* Vol 24

Zazzali, P. (2013) "The Role of Theatre in Society: A Comparative Analysis of the Socio-Cultural Theories of Brecht, Benjamin, and Adorno" assessed from <http://doi.org/10.1080/10848770.2013.774989>. on 28th October, 2020.